

FORMATION OF AN INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE MANAGEMENT OF A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *The article talks about the reforms of the electronic information-educational environment of higher education institutions, their modern stage and the rapidity of the changes taking place in the society. Nowadays, it is important to adapt to the new and higher demands placed on educational institutions as soon as possible and to produce modern requirements and change their existing criteria in terms of their formation.*

Keywords: *e-mail, telecommunication, internet, information, program, resource, multimedia, index.*

The modern stage of educational reforms promotes urgent tasks related to the rapidity of changes taking place in society, faster adaptation to new, higher demands placed on educational institutions. In such conditions, the weight of activities aimed at the development of the educational institution and ensuring its functioning at the level of modern requirements increases continuously. Almost all of the tasks presented in principle create new requirements, and in solving them it is not enough for the team to work only on the basis of existing experience. The analysis of studies on the theory and practice of management of educational institutions shows that the management of an educational institution in modern conditions is directly related to the management of information exchange in it. This, in turn, shows that it is possible to improve the activity of the educational institution due to the effective use of information technologies, and it creates the need to conduct targeted research in this direction.

In our country, as in other countries, requirements for printed and electronic publications are recorded in legal documents. work is known. In Italy, school practice only allows the use of textbooks that have an electronic version, at least downloadable via the Internet. So, it is true that there are printed and electronic versions of the textbook of the same name, and this shows the requirements for their content and structure. A modern textbook that meets the needs of the information society is its cornerstone as the basis of the information-educational environment. The use of a textbook in the usual paper version together with an electronic version based on it is common nowadays. It is clear from this that it is not important to publish it in electronic form or in printed version, the important thing is to be a teaching-methodical set that contains the necessary sets, sets of exercises, and relevant information in any form.

In our opinion, the concept of "electronic information-educational environment" can be defined as a set of software, information-technical, educational-methodical systems that provide a specific goal-oriented educational process. The electronic information-educational environment is characterized according to the following typological signs:

1. The electronic information-educational environment at any level is considered to be an object with a complex structure of a systematic nature.

2. The integrity of the electronic information-educational environment is the same as the concept of achieving systematicity, meaning their harmony, and embodies the educational goals of realizing the personal and professional model of the graduate of the educational institution.

3. The electronic information-educational environment is a factor affecting the effectiveness of education and training, as well as its tool.

In our opinion, it is necessary to introduce a systematic approach to the creation and management of the information learning environment. At the initial stage of this approach, the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution is determined in accordance with the content of modern education. In pedagogical activity, the educational goal performs a systematizing task. It is the defined goal that serves as the basis for choosing the content, purpose, and organizational forms of education. The goal of modern education is to form a system of knowledge, skills and competencies that is formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, and it is reflected in the relevant educational standards. In addition, according to the requirements of the national model of personnel training of our republic, the student becomes not only the object of the pedagogical process, but also its subject.

The purpose of the electronic information-educational environment in the higher pedagogical educational institution is developed in direct connection with the requirements for the future teacher. On the other hand, in the formation of the personality of the future teacher, special attention is paid to the formation of qualities aimed at continuous self-development during the work activity after graduating from the higher pedagogical educational institution. At this point, it should be noted that the educational reforms implemented in our republic require a new interpretation of the concept of "profession". According to the requirements of the national model of personnel training, the owner of a modern profession does not possess a set of ready-made professional knowledge, but he has skills that serve professional development, he can analyze his professional level, he can acquire new knowledge in accordance with the changing requirements of society and production. The basis of the listed qualities is the development process aimed at the implementation of continuous professional training through the acquisition of new knowledge throughout life. In the environment of modern information technologies, the level of improvement of educational content is one of the important conditions for educating a specialist who can meet such requirements.

Today, in the development of the education sector, there are a number of problems related to the use of advanced technologies and educational tools in improving the qualifications of pedagogical staff. The information society has now created new conditions that allow the teacher to manage the students' learning activities. The teaching process is based on the principles of mutual cooperation between the teacher and the learner, and for its improvement, it is necessary to master modern pedagogical and information technologies at a perfect level. In addition, modern information technologies require the teacher to perform a number of important tasks - now the teacher is not only in the field of his specialty, but also in the current teaching concepts, advanced directions in the field of methodology, psychological characteristics of cognition, o should know the possibilities of modern information technologies in teaching. In order to successfully implement this task, it is necessary to continuously work on the effective functioning of the training system, the implementation of advanced educational methods and forms in the field. The traditional system of improving the qualifications of pedagogues of higher education institutions cannot fully satisfy the needs of pedagogues for new information, therefore it is necessary to create

an electronic information-educational environment aimed at ensuring their need for information. In such an environment, pedagogues will have opportunities for distance training.

In the electronic information-educational environment, the independent education of each teacher in terms of improving their qualifications has become crucial, in which they have the opportunity to choose the direction of professional development, the subjects to be studied, and the sources of independent education. will be the improvement of the electronic information-educational environment of the educational institution in accordance with the changing requirements of the information society is an objective necessity of today. The improvement of the informational educational environment requires the following management tasks to be performed:

- setting priorities in accordance with the established goals;
- ensuring the compatibility of the chosen goal and the processes in the educational institution.

Management of the implementation of any goal is required to be clarified at the level of development of the action program. Based on the developed goals, a program for the development of the information-educational environment systems of the institution will be formed, and through their implementation, the necessary conditions will be created for the effective training of specialists based on the requirements of a person-oriented approach. Thus, the organization and management of the informatization of pedagogical educational processes requires the research of the electronic information-educational environment of pedagogical education, the creation of integrated information-educational resources as a factor that increases the quality of education.

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